

Preprint of: Yela, J. R., Crego, A., Buz, J., Sánchez-Zaballos, E., & Gómez-Martínez, M. Á. (2022). Reductions in experiential avoidance explain changes in anxiety, depression and well-being after a mindfulness and self-compassion (MSC) training. *Psychology and Psychotherapy: Theory, Research and Practice*, 95(2), 402-422. <https://doi.org/10.1111/PAPT.12375>

Reductions in Experiential Avoidance Explain Changes in Anxiety, Depression and Wellbeing after a Mindfulness and Self-compassion (MSC) Training

José Ramón Yela¹, Antonio Crego¹, José Buz², Elena Sánchez-Zaballos¹ and María Ángeles Gómez-Martínez¹

¹Department of Psychology. Pontifical University of Salamanca (Spain)

²Department of Education. University of Salamanca (Spain)

Authors' note

Dr. J. R. Yela (ORCID: 0000-0001-9770-4001), Dr. A. Crego (ORCID: 0000-0003-0410-5697), Dra. E. Sánchez-Zaballos (ORCID: 0000-0002-2820-277) and Dra. M. A. Gómez-Martínez (ORCID: 0000-0003-0095-2194) work at the Faculty of Psychology, Pontifical University of Salamanca (Spain). Dr. J. Buz (ORCID: 0000-0002-8526-937X) works at the Faculty of Education, University of Salamanca.

Correspondence concerning this paper should be addressed to Antonio Crego, Faculty of Psychology, Pontifical University of Salamanca, Calle de la Compañía, 5. E37002, Salamanca (SPAIN). Phone: +34 923 277 100. Email: acregodi@upsa.es

Declarations

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethics approval: The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards as laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments. This research received approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the Pontifical University of Salamanca (Minutes of the meeting 15/05/2019). This study was not preregistered.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the MSC trainers that have collaborated in this research very much: Marta Alonso Maynar, Luis Gregoris de la Fuente, Carlos González Díaz, Sara Ponte, Roberto David Alonso Luján, Susana Martín Alvarado, Francisco de Asís Pérez, Óscar Martínez Zulueta, Luis Miguel Amurrio, Ana María de las Heras, M^a del Mar del Pino Martínez, M^a Isabel Rubio Gavidia, and M^a Paz Riol Martínez. We are especially grateful to Dr. Christopher Germer for inspiring and supporting research on the MSC program.

Reductions in Experiential Avoidance Explain Changes in Anxiety, Depression and Wellbeing after a
Mindfulness and Self-compassion (MSC) Training

Abstract

Objective: The Mindfulness and Self-compassion (MSC) protocol has shown efficacy in reducing mental illness symptoms and increasing wellbeing. However, little is known on how the positive outcomes are produced. This study explores how reductions in experiential avoidance following MSC training may explain changes in the participants' levels of anxiety, depression, and wellbeing. *Methods:* The 8-week protocol-based MSC training was delivered to 50 participants, and pre- to post- intervention changes in anxiety, depression and wellbeing were measured. A series of mediation models were conducted, with changes in self-compassion as predictor, changes in experiential avoidance as mediator, and changes in mental health and wellbeing as outcome variables. Point estimates and bootstrap-corrected 95% confidence intervals were calculated to analyze indirect effects through experiential avoidance, by means of structural equation modeling (SEM). *Results:* Following MSC training, participants increased their levels of self-compassion, reduced experiential avoidance, and enhanced mental health (i.e. anxiety and depression symptoms) and wellbeing scores. Increases in self-compassion were associated with decreases in experiential avoidance, which in turn were connected with changes in anxiety, depression and wellbeing from pre- to post-training. The indirect path through changes in experiential avoidance represented moderate to large proportions of the total effects of self-compassion change-scores on anxiety, depression, and wellbeing change-scores. *Conclusions:* Reducing experiential avoidance and increasing psychological flexibility may be a key effect of MSC training linked to improvements of the participants' mental health and wellbeing scores. Self-compassion practices could exert effects on anxiety, depression and wellbeing mainly through promoting reductions in experiential avoidance.

Key words: Mindfulness and Self-Compassion training, self-compassion, experiential avoidance, mental health, wellbeing

Public Health Significance Statements

- This study highlights that the Mindfulness and Self-Compassion program has beneficial effects on anxiety, depression, and wellbeing.
- This study suggests that reductions in experiential avoidance play a key role in self-compassion trainings' effectiveness.

Reductions in Experiential Avoidance Explain Changes in Anxiety, Depression and Wellbeing After a Mindfulness and Self-compassion (MSC) Training.

Introduction

In the last decade, scientific evidence has supported the relationship between the practice of mindfulness and self-compassion and positive psychological outcomes (Neff & Germer, 2013, 2017). In particular, a significant number of studies have focused on evaluating the effectiveness of mindfulness and compassion-based protocols, revealing these programs' beneficial effects concerning the prevention and treatment of mental health issues (Wilson et al., 2019).

The Mindful Self-compassion (MSC) program trains mindfulness skills aimed at managing potentially aversive thoughts, emotions and sensations, while also promoting attitudes of acceptance, openness, and kindness towards oneself and others (Neff & Germer, 2013, 2018; Germer & Neff, 2013a, 2013b, 2019). As Germer (2005) has pointed out, the term 'mindfulness' is a translation of the Pali word '*sati*', which connotes awareness, attention, and remembering. Mindfulness constitutes the core of the Satipatthana Sutta, an influential Buddhist meditation text that teaches paths to progress towards 'awakening' ('*bodhi*'). However, the adoption of the concept of mindfulness in Western psychotherapy has led to an expansion of its meaning beyond its millenary roots. Currently, scientific psychology perspectives on mindfulness connect, somehow, this construct with non-judgment, acceptance, and compassion-related mental qualities (Siegel et al., 2009). Germer (2005, p. 7) himself defines mindfulness as "awareness of present experience with acceptance". According to Neff (2003), self-compassion comprises six components; 'Mindfulness' is a disposition of being fully aware of inner experiences, 'self-kindness' reflects benevolent attitudes towards oneself, and 'common humanity' refers to acknowledging that suffering is inherent to our shared human nature. Their counterparts constitute the three other dimensions: 'over-identification' with painful thoughts, 'self-judgment' or harsh self-criticism, and 'isolation' or feelings of being weird or alienated.

Training self-compassion skills is associated with improvements in wellbeing (Neff & Germer, 2017; Yela, Gómez-Martínez, et al., 2020) and reduced psychopathological symptoms (Friis et al., 2016; Inwood & Ferrari, 2018). Moreover, recent meta-analyses concluded that self-compassion interventions improved the levels of mindfulness and wellbeing, and reduced stress, self-criticism, anxiety and depressive symptoms (Kirby, 2017; Ferrari et al. 2019; Wilson et al., 2019).

Identifying the underlying psychological mechanisms involved in such trainings is a major challenge in this field of research (Ferrari et al., 2019; Neff, 2019). Inwood and Ferrari (2018) have proposed that emotional regulation may mediate the relationship between self-compassion and mental health. Yela, Crego, et al. (2020) have found significant indirect effects of meditation on mental health through three variables: self-compassion, meaning in life/clarification of values, and experiential avoidance. Individuals practicing mindfulness meditation appear to experience higher levels of self-compassion, which presumably will enhance their feelings of meaning in life and will make them more open to accept potentially disturbing inner experiences, as opposed to avoiding thoughts and emotions. Interestingly, experiential avoidance was found to mediate the effects of both self-compassion and meaningfulness on mental health. Results therefore suggested that reducing experiential avoidance could account for, to some extent, the effects of mindfulness meditation and self-compassionate attitudes on mental health. However, studies such as those reviewed by Inwood & Ferrari (2018) and the research by Yela, Crego, et al. (2020), used cross-sectional designs, which may raise doubts concerning the direction of causality. So, a longitudinal analysis of the mechanisms of change involved in self-compassion trainings is yet to be done.

The role of experiential avoidance in mindfulness and self-compassion interventions

Many bridges can be built between Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT; Hayes et al., 1999) and MSC approaches. Not surprisingly, both are included within the third-wave of psychotherapies, and share a contextualist metatheory (Germer, 2005; Hayes, 1993, 2002). As Neff & Tirch (2013) have

recommended, research on self-compassion may benefit from analysing how self-compassion is associated with ACT constructs such as acceptance, perspective taking, and psychological flexibility.

‘Experiential avoidance’, a central concept in ACT, refers to the tendency of people to escape or run away from those internal experiences (e.g. sensations, emotions, thoughts, memories) that may generate discomfort or suffering in our lives (Hayes et al., 1999). This construct is highly connected with the cultivation of ‘acceptance’ that the MSC program aims to promote. In the context of the Mindfulness and Self-Compassion training, acceptance refers to the ability of allowing present moment experiences – whether pleasurable, neutral or painful– to be just as they are (Germer, 2005). In this regard, acceptance entails exposure to experience, as opposed to any sort of avoidant behaviour.

Interestingly, experiential avoidance has been suggested as a key explanatory mechanism of treatment effects on mental health, and has been proposed as a transdiagnostic functional contextual factor involved in psychopathology (Boulanger et al., 2010); this proposal has implications for both psychological assessment models and therapeutic interventions (Barlow et al., 2017). In this regard, the role of experiential avoidance in relation to MSC interventions is worth analysing.

As both cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses have revealed, avoiding potentially disturbing inner experiences predicts increases in anxiety and depression and reductions in wellbeing (Machell et al., 2015; Moroz & Dunkley, 2019; Yela, Crego, et al., 2020).

Negative correlations between self-compassion and emotional and experiential avoidance (Gillanders et al., 2015; Marshall and Brockman, 2016) have been already reported. Moreover, Costa and Pinto-Gouveia (2013) found significant positive correlations between experiential avoidance and depression, anxiety, and stress, and negative significant associations between self-compassion and these outcome variables, in a sample of adults with chronic pain. The authors emphasized the role of experiential avoidance and self-compassion as factors that mostly explain psychological distress.

Experiential avoidance may play a key role concerning the connection between self-compassionate attitudes and mental health. Here, Moroz and Dunkley (2019) found that experiential

avoidance mediated the relationship between self-critical perfectionism and both depressive and anxious symptoms.

Alda et al. (2016) found that expert meditators had a low tendency to experiential avoidance compared to non-meditators. The practice of meditation may encourage acceptance and promote a decrease in experiential avoidance behaviors. They further proposed that experiential avoidance may have a mediating role in the beneficial outcomes derived from meditation practice. Likewise, reductions in experiential avoidance have been suggested as a transdiagnostic mechanism in cognitive-behavioral therapy. In particular, changes in experiential avoidance have been found to be associated with changes in anxiety symptoms following cognitive-behavioral interventions (Eustis et al., 2020).

The present study

In this context, we analyse whether training participants in a self-compassion protocol (MSC) will produce changes in anxiety, depression and psychological wellbeing, and especially, whether those changes may be explained by changes in experiential avoidance. The MSC program includes exposure to difficult emotions/thoughts as one of the main competencies/skills trained throughout its 8 sessions. Thus, clarifying the role of prompting exposure vs. avoidance is expected to shed light on why the MSC protocol may be an effective training. In particular, our study aims to test four hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1 (H1). The increases in self-compassion following MSC training will be associated with decreases in anxiety and depression symptoms, and improvements in wellbeing.

Hypothesis 2 (H2). The increases in self-compassion following MSC training will be connected with a decline in the participants' levels of experiential avoidance.

Hypothesis 3 (H3). The changes in experiential avoidance will be associated with enhanced mental health and wellbeing.

Hypothesis 4 (H4). The changes in experiential avoidance following MSC training may be able to account for, to some extent, the relationship between changes in self-compassion and changes in anxiety, depression and wellbeing.

For all hypotheses, we will analyze self-compassion total scores, and we will separately explore the role of each component of self-compassion. As Chio et al. (2021) have recently found, the dimensions of self-compassion may be associated with psychological distress and wellbeing with a different strength. Moreover, Neff et al. (2018) have recommended that, for researchers interested in unpacking the mechanisms of how self-compassion enhances wellbeing, examining the six constituent components of self-compassion may be useful. In any case, as Dreisoerner et al. (2020) have suggested, the components of self-compassion are connected to each other. Thus, we expect that the increases in mindfulness, common humanity perceptions, and self-kindness, and reductions in over-identification, isolation, and self-judgment after the MSC training will be associated with decreases in experiential avoidance, anxiety, depression and increases in wellbeing.

Methods

Sample

The sample comprised 50 participants (43 women and 7 men) between 31 and 68 years old, with a mean age of 49.78 ($SD=10.37$). Most were in active employment (38 participants), with 6 retired persons, and 6 reporting other situations (unemployed persons, workers on medical leave, or students). As regards educational level, 18 participants had postgraduate studies, 21 had graduate university studies, 6 attended high school or vocational training, and 6 reported having elementary studies. Regarding their nationality, 35 participants were from Spain and 15 from Portugal.

Sensitivity analyses were carried out using G*Power software (Faul et al., 2007), assuming $\alpha = .05$, $1-\beta = .80$, and two-tailed contrasts. Results revealed that, using a $N = 50$ sample, moderate effects ($d_z = 0.40$) could be detected for paired-samples pre- post- analyses; also moderate effects ($f^2 = 0.16$) could be identified in multiple regression-based analyses with four predictors (i.e. two control variables, the independent variable, and de mediator variable). Therefore, taking into account that previous meta-analyses on the effects of MSC have reported moderate effect sizes (Ferrari et al., 2019; Wilson et al., 2019), the sample size was considered adequate for this study purposes.

Design and procedure

A quasi-experimental design was used, with a group of participants receiving MSC training as well as a collection of pre- and post-intervention measures. Participants were recruited among people attending MSC trainings delivered in collaborating institutions in Spain and Portugal, from May 2019 to December 2019. Prior to participation, all individuals were informed about the purposes and characteristics of the research study and the MSC training, and signed the informed consent. Participation in this research was voluntary and trainees did not receive any compensation for their collaboration. The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards as laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its later amendments. This research has received approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the Pontifical University of Salamanca (Minutes of the meeting 15/05/2019).

Pre- and post-intervention measures were gathered by means of an online questionnaire, designed using the Google Forms web-based tool, and stored on the institutional Google Drive of the research team. Then, a link to the questionnaire was generated and sent to participants by email. In order to avoid missing values, all the questionnaire items were defined as “required-question” in Google Forms tool (i.e. a response is needed to proceed to the next screen of the questionnaire). Once the participant completed the survey, his/her responses were submitted online and automatically received in an Excel file located on the research team’s Google Drive.

The MSC training was provided by clinical psychologists accredited as a MSC Certified Teachers by the University of California and the Center for Mindful Self-Compassion (San Diego, Ca, USA). The MSC training protocol consists of 8 weekly 2.5 hour group sessions (Germer and Neff, 2013a, 2013b; Germer and Neff, 2019). Participants were trained in formal (i.e. meditation-based) and informal (i.e. self-compassion exercises) mindfulness and self-compassion practices. They were also instructed to complete homework, aiming at reinforcing skills learned in session. An overview of the MSC sessions is presented in Table 1.

A total of 80 individuals attending MSC trainings were offered to participate in this research. Complete pre- and post- measures were obtained from 50 participants (participation rate = 62.5%).

Data analyses

Descriptive statistics were calculated (Mean and Standard Deviation) and paired samples *t*-tests were carried out, in order to analyze differences from the pre-intervention to post-intervention time of measurement. The r^2 statistic was calculated as an effect-size measure, showing the magnitude of changes observed from pre- to post-training. Because the cultural differences between samples could be a potential confounding factor, we conducted a two-way mixed ANOVA with nationality as between-subject factor, and time as intra-subject factor, in order to test the effect of this variable on the results.

Change-scores (standardized residuals method) were calculated and used in mediation analyses. Following Hayes (2009, 2018), a bootstrapping-based method was used to test total, indirect (i.e. mediated) and direct effects. Point estimates and 95% bias-corrected (BC) bootstrap confidence intervals (percentile method) were obtained using 5000 bootstrap samples. According to this procedure, when zero is not included between the lower and upper bound of the BC confidence interval for the indirect effects, statistically significant mediated effects, different from zero with 95% confidence, are obtained. The ratio of the indirect effect to the total effect was calculated as an effect-size measure for mediation effects. This ratio is usually reported as an index of the relative magnitude of the mediation path (Preacher & Kelley, 2011). A series of mediation analyses were conducted. Self-compassion total change-scores and change-scores corresponding to 6 self-compassion components (self-kindness, common humanity, mindfulness, self-judgement, isolation, and over-identification) were included as predictors in separate models. Experiential avoidance change-scores were included as the mediator variable in all models. Anxiety change-scores, depression change-scores and wellbeing change-scores, were included in separate models as outcome variables. Thus, a total of 21 mediation models were tested. The potential confounding effects of age and sex were controlled for in all mediation analyses.

All analyses were carried out using the statistical package IBM SPSS 19 and AMOS 16 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA).

Instruments and measures

Self-compassion. The Self-Compassion Scale (SCS) was used (Neff, 2003, 2016; Spanish adaptation by García-Campayo et al., 2014; Portuguese adaptation by Castilho and Pinto-Gouveia, 2011). The scale has 26 items to assess dispositions to self-kindness rather than self-criticism, mindful awareness rather than over-identification with distressing inner experiences, and feeling that such experiences are common to human beings rather than feeling isolated or weird. A total self-compassion score, as well as six self-compassion's components scores were computed. Reliability was estimated for the total scale (pre-test: $\alpha = .94$; post-test: $\alpha = .97$) and the subscales; self-kindness (pre-test: $\alpha = .89$; post-test: $\alpha = .90$), common humanity (pre-test: $\alpha = .81$; post-test: $\alpha = .81$), mindfulness (pre-test: $\alpha = .86$; post-test: $\alpha = .86$), self-judgement (pre-test: $\alpha = .81$; post-test: $\alpha = .91$), isolation (pre-test: $\alpha = .78$; post-test: $\alpha = .82$), and over-identification (pre-test: $\alpha = .79$; post-test: $\alpha = .77$).

Experiential avoidance. The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II) was used (Hayes, 2005; Bond et al., 2011). This scale measures the respondent's unwillingness to be exposed to and accept potentially disturbing inner experiences (e.g., thoughts, feelings, memories, sensations) even when avoidant behaviour could be inconsistent with the individual's values and goals. The AAQ-II is usually used in the field of ACT-related processes research as a measure of 'psychological inflexibility' or 'experiential avoidance'. As mentioned, these constructs constitute a core explanatory mechanism for psychological problems according to this therapy approach. Although the two terms are commonly used interchangeably, Bond et al (2011, p. 678) have specified that 'psychological inflexibility' refers to "the rigid dominance of psychological reactions, over chosen values and contingencies, in guiding action" while 'experiential avoidance' refers to "the attempt to alter the form, frequency, or situational sensitivity of difficult private events". Therefore, as Ruiz et al. (2013) have pointed out, 'psychological flexibility'

would be a broader concept that includes all sort of inner experiences, within which ‘experiential avoidance’ –focused on negative inner experiences– is entailed.

Spanish respondents answered the 10-item Spanish adaptation of AAQ-II developed by Patrón Espinosa (2010). This scale comprises 7 negatively worded items (i.e. indicative of cognitive inflexibility/experiential avoidance) and 3 positively worded items (i.e. indicative of psychological flexibility/acceptance). Responses to positive items are reversed prior to calculating a total score. For Portuguese respondents, the Spanish version by Patron Espinosa (2010) was adapted by means of a forward and back translation method. In addition, the 7-item Portuguese adaptation by Pinto-Gouveia et al. (2012), which uses only negatively worded items, was contrasted with the Portuguese version of items produced by translators. Minor adjustments concerning the wording of items, and the addition of 3 positively worded items to the original Portuguese scale adaptation, were required to guarantee that Spanish and Portuguese versions of AAQ-II items were equivalent and retained the meaning of validated items. Positively worded Portuguese items were also reverse scored prior to calculation of total scores.

Additional analyses were carried out on pre-test measures in order to determine the psychometric properties of the AAQ-II scale used. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), using principal components analysis and direct oblimin rotation method, revealed a unifactorial structure of the 10 items scale that accounted for 57.56 % of variance [$KMO = 0.88$; Bartlett test of sphericity: $\chi^2(45) = 308.15, p < .000$]. All items presented factor loads $> .53$. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) also revealed an excellent fit of data to a one-factor scale structure ($\chi^2 = 35.72, df = 33, p = .339$; $\chi^2/df = 1.085$; $CFI = .99$; $SRMR = .05$; $RMSEA = .04$), after allowing for correlated measurement errors for items 3 and 5, and 7 and 9. In our sample, reliability for AAQ-II was $\alpha = .91$ (pre-test) and $\alpha = .90$ (post-test).

Anxiety and depression. The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale(HAD) was used (Zigmond & Snaith, 1983; Spanish adaptation by Terol et al., 2007; Portuguese adaptation by Pais-Ribeiro et al., 2007). This scale comprises 7 items aimed at measuring anxiety symptoms and 7 items intended to

identify depression problems. For HAD-anxiety reliability was $\alpha = .87$ (pre-test) and $\alpha = .88$ (post-test). Reliability for HAD-depression was $\alpha = .87$ (pre-test) and $\alpha = .86$ (post-test).

Psychological wellbeing. The total score of the 29-item Spanish adaptation of the Ryff's (1989) Psychological Wellbeing Scales was used (Díaz et al., 2006). As a Portuguese version of this adapted scale is not available, the items were translated from the Spanish into Portuguese. Forward and backward translation procedures were used. The scale's total score represents a global wellbeing measure, calculated from wellbeing components such as self-acceptance, positive relationships with others, autonomy, control of one's life, purpose in life, and personal growth. Reliability for PWBS was $\alpha = .95$ (pre-test) and $\alpha = .94$ (post-test).

Results

As shown in Table 2, after the MSC training, participants increased their total scores for self-compassion, as well as their scores for self-kindness, common humanity and mindfulness. Conversely, they reduced their levels of self-judgment, isolation and over-identification from pre- to post-intervention. The changes, considering the r^2 effect-size, were of a great magnitude for all measures. Regarding outcome variables, there were significant decreases in anxiety and depression scores after the MSC program, with moderate effect-size. A larger increase in terms of effect-size, on the other hand, was observed for the wellbeing scores, also showing significant differences across moments of measurement.

Concerning the patterns of change from pre- to post-training, a series of two-way mixed ANOVA revealed no differences by nationality. The interaction of nationality by time was not significant for self-compassion total scores ($F_{1,48} = 2.47, p=.123$), common humanity ($F_{1,48} = 1.56, p=.217$), mindfulness ($F_{1,48} = 0.75, p=.389$), self-judgment ($F_{1,48} = 0.34, p=.565$), isolation ($F_{1,48} = 1.20, p=.279$), over-identification ($F_{1,48} = 1.64, p=.207$), experiential avoidance ($F_{1,48} = 1.64, p=.207$), anxiety ($F_{1,48} = 1.06, p=.308$), depression ($F_{1,48} = 0.005, p=.942$), or wellbeing ($F_{1,48} = 0.52, p=.474$). Self-kindness was an exception where a significant nationality by time interaction was found ($F_{1,48} = 5.52, p=.023$), with Portuguese participants reporting greater increases in self-kindness (pre: Mean = 2.36, $SD = 0.68$; post:

Mean = 3.60, $SD = 0.52$) as compared with Spanish trainees (pre: Mean = 2.86, $SD = 0.91$; post: Mean = 3.56, $SD = 0.87$). Thus, the effects of nationality will be controlled for in mediation analyses involving self-kindness.

Overall effects of changes in self-compassion on changes in mediating and outcome variables

The change in self-compassion total scores showed significant overall effects on the outcome variables –i.e., on changes in anxiety, depression and psychological wellbeing (Table 3). Similarly, the change in each of the six SCS self-compassion scale's scores also produced significant total effects on anxiety, depression and psychological wellbeing change-scores. As expected, the increase in the participants' overall level of self-compassion was associated with reductions in anxiety and depression, and increases in psychological wellbeing. Thus, H1 was confirmed. The same pattern was observed for the relationships of self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness change-scores with changes in the outcome variables. Conversely, decreases in levels of self-judgment, isolation and over-identification were significantly associated with reductions in anxiety and depression, and improvements in psychological wellbeing.

As predicted in H2, increases in self-compassion were related with decreases in the participants' levels of experiential avoidance (Table 4). Total SCS, self-kindness, common humanity and mindfulness change-scores were negatively related with changes in experiential avoidance, whereas changes in self-judgment, isolation and over-identification were positively related to avoidance. Moreover, as predicted in H3, changes in experiential avoidance were positively associated with depression and anxiety change-scores, and negatively associated with wellbeing change-scores (Table 5).

The change in self-compassion total scores explained 50% of the change in experiential avoidance, which can be considered a strong association in terms of effect-size (Table 6). The changes in each of SCS components was moderately related to changes in experiential avoidance, with percentages of explained variance ranging from 29% (common humanity) to 38% (self-judgment and isolation).

Overall, the models, where self-compassion (total) change-scores are included as a predictor and experiential avoidance change-scores are included as a mediator, were able to explain large percentages of the outcome variables change-scores (Table 6). They explained 70% of the change in wellbeing, 48% of the change in depression, and 45% of the change in anxiety levels. The mediation models constructed using each of the SCS components, again, were able to explain large proportions of the variance in mental health and wellbeing change-scores. For instance, changes in the SCS components explained between 69% (mindfulness change-scores) and 56% (common humanity change-scores) of changes in wellbeing. Changes in self-kindness accounted for 45% of changes in depression, and 49% of changes in depression were accounted for by changes in over-identification. Finally, concerning changes in anxiety scores, the models using the dimensions of self-compassion could explain between 40% (isolation) and 53% (over-identification) of variance.

Mediating effects of changes in self-compassion through experiential avoidance on outcome variables

The analyses of the indirect effects showed that changes in experiential avoidance significantly mediated the relationship between changes in self-compassion variables (SCS total and subscales' change-scores) and changes in the outcome variables (Table 7). Thus, H4 was confirmed. The indirect effects through changes in experiential avoidance represented 41.81%, 54.24% and 19.95%, of the total effects that changes in self-compassion produced on anxiety, depression and wellbeing change-scores, respectively. Moreover, the indirect effects represented between 31.53% and 64.18% of the total effects that each SCS component change-scores had on anxiety change-scores, between 51.97% and 73.53% of total effects on depression change-scores, and between 28.97% and 46.82% of total effects on wellbeing change-scores.

Interestingly, the results point to a complete mediating effect for the relationship between changes in self-compassion (total and SCS components) and changes in depression, except for over-identification, where a partial mediation was identified. As shown in Table 4, when experiential avoidance change-

scores are included as a mediator in the model, the direct effect of self-compassion change-scores (total and SCS components, except for over-identification) on depression change-scores has no statistical significance. Moreover, some complete mediation effects were also observed for mediation models involving self-compassion (total and SCS components), experiential avoidance, and anxiety change-scores. In this case, the direct effect of self-kindness change-scores, common humanity, mindfulness, self-judgment and isolation is devoid of statistical significance when experiential avoidance change-scores are included in the model (Table 4). As regards wellbeing, partial mediation effects were observed, with significant direct effects of self-compassion (total and SCS components change-scores) on changes in wellbeing despite the inclusion of experiential avoidance change-scores in the models (Table 4).

Discussion

This study contributes by shedding light on how MSC training may produce beneficial effects. As presented, following the training, participants decreased their scores in anxiety and depression and increased their levels of wellbeing. This result is in line with previous research by Neff & Germer (2013, 2018), Germer and Neff (2013a, 2013b, 2019), and Friis et al, (2016) who found that the MSC program succeeded in improving mental health, mindfulness, self-compassion and wellbeing scores. However, to date, knowledge on the mechanisms by which MSC may lead to such positive outcomes are scarce.

Previous research has found that the effects of mindfulness meditation on mental health may be accounted for by self-compassion, meaning in life, and experiential avoidance (Moroz & Dunkley, 2019; Yela, Crego, et al., 2020). However, the study by Yela, Crego, et al. (2020) used cross-sectional data, and it was not specifically focused on MSC trainees but on general population practicing mindfulness meditation, which limited the scope of conclusions. Furthermore, the longitudinal study by Moroz & Dunkley (2019), did not measure self-compassion but a closely related construct, i.e. self-critical perfectionism. Moreover, their participants did not receive any sort of intervention. In this regard, the present study represents an improvement, as it allows analyzing changes after a protocol-based MSC training and identifying the key role played by experiential avoidance. As reported, to a great extent, the

association between changes in self-compassion and changes in mental health and wellbeing measures could be explained by reductions in experiential avoidance after the MSC training.

The role of experiential avoidance as a variable significantly involved in mental health issues has been consistently highlighted in previous research. For instance, experiential avoidance has been linked to mental health issues, such as panic (Karekla et al., 2004) and generalized anxiety disorder (Roemer et al., 2005). In addition, the lack of willingness to endure anxiety is identified as a predictor of anxiety-related problems, and more than half of the variation in depressive symptoms may be attributed to lack of acceptance of painful experiences according to Hayes, Strosahl et al. (2004). Similar results have highlighted the relevant role of acceptance concerning the management of a variety of problems, such as physical pain (Dahl et al., 2004), head trauma and spinal cord injuries, heart attacks and other areas of physical illness or damage (Melamed et al., 1992; Riegel, 1993), diabetes (Gregg et al., 2007) and substance use relapses (Litman et al., 1984), among others.

Particularly relevant, concerning our study's purpose, is the research by Costa and Pinto-Gouveia (2013), who carried out a series of hierarchical regression analyses in a Portuguese sample of adults with chronic pain. As may be observed in their analyses, experiential avoidance plays a mediating role in the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms, even after controlling for the effect of different types of coping strategies. Our result is highly consistent with this finding. From the results of Costa and Pinto-Gouveia (2013), however, no mediational effects of experiential avoidance on the relationship between self-compassion and anxiety can be inferred, unlike what was found in our study. However, it should be noted that, beyond the different samples used, this study is different from ours in some respects. For instance, these authors conducted analyses in which they included coping strategies as predictor variables and used cross-sectional data. In any case, the prominent role of self-compassion and experiential avoidance in explaining depressive and anxiety symptoms is something that both Pinto-Gouveia's (2013) and our study agree on.

From the ACT perspective, experiential avoidance causes suffering in people by motivating constant and continuous responses of escape and avoidance, maintained by negative reinforcement. Conversely, exposure to experience while developing an attitude of acceptance may contribute to coping with painful internal events (Hayes et al., 1990). In training situations, acceptance is frequently developed through the practice of meditation, and has been found to be inversely connected with experiential avoidance behaviors (Alda et al., 2016). In this line, previous research has already suggested that exposure to emotions, thoughts and body sensations may be cited among the mechanisms explaining mindfulness' positive outcomes (Baer, 2009; Gu, et al., 2015; Hölzel et al., 2011; Shapiro et al., 2006; Treanor, 2011). From our point of view, the capacity of acceptance may be operationalized as a basic psychological process of exposure to interoceptive sensations, emotions, and thoughts that generate discomfort in the subjects. The use of exposure-based strategies pervades the MSC protocol. In particular, two sessions of this program are explicitly dedicated to this aim: “managing difficult emotions” (session 6) and “transforming difficult relationships” (session 7).

Interestingly, the mediation models tested were able to explain larger proportions of variance in wellbeing change-scores (up to 70% of explained variance), compared with anxiety and depression change-scores (less than 50% of explained variance). Thus, changes in self-compassion, overall, appeared to be relatively more connected with increases in wellbeing, compared with reductions in anxiety and depression. However, when the ratio indirect effects to total effects is considered, experiential avoidance may play a more relevant role concerning changes in anxiety and depression, compared with the more moderate ratios obtained as regards wellbeing. This finding may suggest that the beneficial effects of self-compassion on mental health could be attributed, to a large extent, to exposure processes. Such exposure processes would be also important, although to a lesser extent, to explain increases in wellbeing derived from self-compassion. Self-compassion is strongly associated with wellbeing. However, in addition to experiential avoidance, other mediating mechanisms should be explored in order to better explain the connection between self-compassion and wellbeing.

Limitations and future research

An obvious limitation of our study is the lack of a control group. This point could certainly limit the conclusions about the efficacy of the MSC program that can be drawn from our research. However, as mentioned, numerous studies have already addressed this issue and pointed to the benefits of the MSC training, and our study has also found results coherent with other studies analyzing MSC effectiveness. In any case, the main focus of the present research was not testing MSC program's efficacy but to analyze why changes in mental health and wellbeing occur after levels of self-compassion are increased, i.e. finding mediating mechanisms. Another limitation concerns the small sample size. This aspect may limit the possibilities of generalizing the results and detecting small effect-sizes. The participation rate in our study was rather low, and we had no opportunity to analyse potential differences between those who completed pre and post-test measures and those who did not. We must note, however, that participation in this study was completely voluntary and that not taking part in this research does not necessarily mean an individual abandoned the MSC training. In any case, a relevant issue for future research would be the analysis of sociodemographic, motivational, or other variables that may have an effect on training participation.

Furthermore, the reduced number of subjects has constrained the elaboration of more complex mediation models (for instance, including two or more mediators), since the recommended number of variables to be introduced in the analyses depends on the size of the sample. As shown, interoceptive exposure, measured through reductions in experiential avoidance, largely explains the changes in anxiety, depression and wellbeing. This result reveals that acceptance attitudes, as opposed to avoidant behaviors, are a powerful tool provided by the MSC program, which may shed light on self-compassion trainings' pathways of action. However, other mediating mechanisms may be also responsible for the MSC program's effectiveness. As already pointed out, previous studies have suggested the role that emotion regulation (Inwood & Ferrari, 2018) and clarifying values and finding meaning in life may play (Yela,

Crego, et al., 2020). The MSC program works also on such aspects. For instance, session 5 is devoted to “identifying personal values” and session 6 works on “managing difficult emotions”.

To overcome these limitations, it is advisable to carry out new research with larger samples and use of a control group, incorporating randomization. It would also be interesting to explore additional mechanisms of mediation, such as possible changes in cognitive defusion, meaningfulness, behavioral activation, emotion regulation, etc. after the MSC training.

Another possible limitation comes from the use of the AAQ-II scale, about which some authors have raised doubts concerning construct validity (Wolgast, 2014) and discriminant validity (Tyndall et al., 2019). Although such concerns have been identified, and the need for integrating new instruments into ACT-related research has been acknowledged, the AAQ-II remains a widely used measure of cognitive inflexibility/experiential avoidance (Rogge et al., 2019).

A possible cause for concern may come from the use of 10-item versions of the AAQ-II in our study. Bond et al. (2011) subsequently reduced the scale to 7 items by eliminating the three positively worded items, as these items appeared to load on a second factor, which could be a methodological artefact. In our analyses, once the scores of the positively worded items were reversed, the 10-item scale clearly yielded a unifactorial solution, with very good psychometric properties and high reliability. Bond et al. (2011) themselves, and other researchers, have expressed that using the 10-item version, consisting of 7 negatively worded items and 3 reversed-score positive items, is very common in the research literature and does not invalidate the results obtained, as the 7-item and 10-item AAQ-II present similar psychometric properties (Rogge et al., 2019; Ruiz et al., 2013). In our study, great efforts were made to ensure that the Spanish and Portuguese items were equivalent in content and appearance, using scale versions with the same number of items. The absence of significant differences in AAQ-II scores between Spanish and Portuguese participants may be indicating that this objective was accomplished. Moreover, we opted for the longer version of the scale for several reasons. First, from a conceptual point of view, the 3 positively worded items appeared to refer to relevant aspects of psychological flexibility/acceptance,

and the possible causes for concern associated to them are well resolved by reversing their scores. Secondly, as known, a scale's reliability as measured by Cronbach's alpha is dependent on the sample size and the number of items in the scale. Therefore, we preferred a longer version of AAQ-II in order to prevent potential reliability problems, considering that just a small sample will be gathered. In a similar line, Rogge et al. (2019) have recommended the use of longer scales in the field of ACT-processes research. In any case, replication studies using other measures of experiential avoidance and other versions of AAQ-II (i.e. 7-item scale) are highly encouraged for future research.

Also interesting for future research is the study of possible cultural factors that impact self-compassion. We found differences in self-kindness between Spanish and Portuguese participants. However, a deeper analysis of this issue is beyond the scope of the present study. More studies with diverse populations are therefore needed.

Practical implications

This study provides additional evidence of the potential benefits of the MSC training. Moreover, the results suggest that reducing experiential avoidance is a key component in this training's effectiveness. In this sense, clinical and health psychologists are encouraged to work on and reinforce aspects related to exposure to experience that are present in the MSC protocol. For example, the exercises "working with difficult emotions" and "working with shame" in session 6 ("Managing difficult emotions"); or the exercises "exploring difficult relationships" and "compassion with equanimity" in session 7 ("Transforming difficult relationships") may be especially useful to accomplish this aim. However, either explicit or implicitly, the attitude of acceptance/exposure to potentially unpleasant feelings is trained throughout most of the MSC program's sessions. For instance, in session 1 ("What is self-compassion?") through the practice named "the self-compassion pause", in session 2 ("Practicing mindfulness") by means of different mindfulness exercises, and in sessions 3 ("Taking care of yourself") and 4 ("Self-compassion") using loving-kindness practices aimed at handling self-criticism.

Promoting psychological flexibility and exposure to potentially disturbing inner experiences in a self-compassionate manner may contribute to enhance psychological training aimed at increasing wellbeing and preventing mental health issues. Programs such as the MSC protocol, where exposure to experience through mindfulness and self-compassionate practices is present, may offer powerful tools to accomplish those objectives.

References

- Alda, M., Puebla-Guedea, M., Rodero, B., Demarzo, M., Montero-Marin, J., Roca, M. & Garcia-Campayo, J. (2016). Zen-meditation, length of telomeres, and the role of experiential avoidance and compassion. *Mindfulness*, 7(3), 651-659. doi:10.1007/s12671-016-0500-5.
- Baer, R. A. (2009). Self-focused attention and mechanisms of change in mindfulness-based treatment. *Cognitive Behaviour Therapy*, 38, 15–20. doi:10.1080/16506070902980703.
- Barlow, D. H., Farchione, T. J., Bullis, J. R., et al. (2017). The Unified Protocol for Transdiagnostic Treatment of Emotional Disorders Compared With Diagnosis-Specific Protocols for Anxiety Disorders: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 74(9), 875–884. doi:10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2017.2164
- Bond, F. W., Hayes, S. C., Baer, R. A., Carpenter, K. M., Guenole, N. Orcutt, H. K.,... & Zettle, R. D. (2011). Preliminary psychometric properties of the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II: A revised measure of psychological flexibility and experiential avoidance. *Behavior Therapy*, 42, 676-688. <https://doi:10.1016/j.beth.2011.03.007>.
- Boulanger, J. L., Hayes, S. C., & Pistorello, J. (2010). Experiential avoidance as a functional contextual concept. In A. M. Kring & D. M. Sloan (Eds.), *Emotion regulation and psychopathology: A transdiagnostic approach to etiology and treatment* (pp. 107–136). New York: The Guilford Press.

- Castilho, P., & Pinto-Gouveia, J. (2011). Self-Compassion: Validation of the Portuguese version of the Self-Compassion Scale and its relation with early negative experiences, social comparison and psychopathology. *Psychologica*, *54*, 203-231. doi:10.14195/1647-8606_54_8.
- Chio, F. H., Mak, W. W., & Ben, C. L. (2021). Meta-analytic review on the differential effects of self-compassion components on well-being and psychological distress: The moderating role of dialecticism on self-compassion. *Clinical Psychology Review*, *85*, 101986. doi:doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2021.101986
- Dahl, J., Wilson, K., & Nilsson, A. (2004). Acceptance and commitment therapy and the treatment of persons at risk for long-term disability resulting from stress and pain symptoms: A preliminary randomized trial. *Behavior Therapy*, *35*(4), 785-801. doi:10.1016/S0005-7894(04)80020-0.
- Díaz, D., Rodríguez-Carvajal, R., Blanco, A., Moreno-Jiménez, B., Gallardo, I., Valle, C., & Van Dierendonck, D. (2006). Adaptación española de las escalas de bienestar psicológico de Ryff. *Psicothema*, *18*(3), 572-577.
- Dreisoerner, A., Junker, N. M., & Van Dick, R. (2020). The relationship among the components of self-compassion: A pilot study using a compassionate writing intervention to enhance self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, *22*, 21-47. doi: 10.1007/s10902-019-00217-4.
- Eustis, E. H., Cardona, N., Nauphal, M., Sauer-Zavala, S., Rosellini, A. J., Farchione, T. J., & Barlow, D. H. (2020). Experiential avoidance as a mechanism of change across cognitive-behavioral therapy in a sample of participants with heterogeneous anxiety disorders. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, *44*(2), 275-286. doi: 10.1007/s10608-019-10063-6.
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Lang, A.-G., & Buchner, A. (2007). G*Power 3: A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behavior Research Methods*, *39*, 175-191

- Ferrari, M., Hunt, C., Harrysunker, A., Abbott, M. J., Beath, A. P., & Einstein, D. A. (2019). Self-Compassion Interventions and Psychosocial Outcomes: a Meta-Analysis of RCTs. *Mindfulness*, *10* (8), 1455–1473. doi: 10.1007/s12671-019-01134-6.
- Friis, A. M., Johnson, M. H., Cutfield, R. G., & Consedine, N. S. (2016). Kindness matters: a randomized controlled trial of a mindful self-compassion intervention improves depression, distress, and HbA1c among patients with diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, *39*(11):1963-1971. doi: 10.2337/dc16-0416.
- Garcia-Campayo, J., Navarro-Gil, M., Andrés, E., Montero-Marin, J., López-Artal, L., & Demarzo, M. M. P. (2014). Validation of the Spanish versions of the long (26 items) and short (12 items) forms of the Self-Compassion Scale (SCS). *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, *12*(1), 4. doi:10.1186/1477-7525-12-4.
- Germer, C. K. (2005). Mindfulness: What is it? What does it matter? In C.K. Germer, R.D. Siegel, & P. R. Fulton (Eds.), *Mindfulness and Psychotherapy*. (pp. 3 - 27). New York: The Guilford Press.
- Germer, C., & Neff, K. (2013a). Self-compassion in clinical practice. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, *69*(8), 856-867. doi:10.1002/jclp.22021.
- Germer, C. & Neff, K. (2013b). The Mindful Self-Compassion training program. In T. Singer & M. Bolz (Eds.) *Compassion: Bridging theory and practice: A multimedia book* (pp. 365-396). Leipzig, Germany: Max-Planck Institute. Retrieved from: <http://www.compassion-training.org/>
- Germer, C., & Neff, K. (2019). *Teaching the mindful self-compassion program: A guide for professionals*. New York: Guilford Publications.
- Gillanders, D. T., Sinclair, A. K., MacLean, M., & Jardine, K. (2015). Illness cognitions, cognitive fusion, avoidance and self-compassion as predictors of distress and quality of life in a heterogeneous sample of adults, after cancer. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, *4*(4), 300-311. doi:10.1016/j.jcbs.2015.07.003.

- Gregg, J. A., Callaghan, G. M., Hayes, S. C., & Glenn-Lawson, J. L. (2007). Improving diabetes self-management through acceptance, mindfulness, and values: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 75*(2), 336. doi:10.1037/0022-006X.75.2.336.
- Gu, J., Strauss, C., Bond, R., & Cavanagh, K. (2015). How do mindfulness-based cognitive therapy and mindfulness-based stress reduction improve mental health and wellbeing? A systematic review and meta-analysis of mediation studies. *Clinical Psychology Review, 37*, 1–12. doi:10.1016/j.cpr.2015.01.006.
- Hayes, A. F. (2009). Beyond Baron and Kenny: Statistical mediation analysis in the new millennium. *Communication Monographs, 76*, 408-420. doi:10.1080/03637750903310360.
- Hayes, A. F. (2018). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Hayes, S.C. (1993). Analytic goals and the varieties of scientific contextualism. In S. C. Hayes, L. J. Hayes, H. W. Reese, & T. R. Sarbin (Eds.), *Varieties of scientific contextualism* (pp. 11–27). Reno, NV: Context Press.
- Hayes, S.C. (2002). Acceptance, mindfulness, and science. *Clinical Psychology: Science and Practice, 9*(1), 101–106. doi: 10.1093/clipsy.9.1.101
- Hayes, S.C. (2005). *The ACT packet*. Retrieved from: https://www.actmindfully.com.au/upimages/act_pack.pdf
- Hayes, S.C., Strosahl, K. D. & Wilson, K. G. (1999). *Acceptance and Commitment therapy: An experiential approach to behaviour change*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Hayes, S.C., Strosahl, K., Wilson, K.G. et al. (2004). Measuring experiential avoidance: A preliminary test of a working model. *Psychological Record 54*, 553–578. doi:10.1007/BF03395492.
- Hölzel, B. K., Lazar, S. W., Gard, T., Schuman-Olivier, Z., Vago, D. R., & Ott, U. (2011). How does mindfulness meditation work? Proposing mechanisms of action from a conceptual and neural

perspective. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 6(6), 537–559.

doi:10.1177/1745691611419671.

Inwood, E. & Ferrari, M. (2018). Mechanisms of change in the relationship between self-compassion, emotion regulation, and mental health: a systematic review. *Applied Psychology: Health and Wellbeing*, 10(2), 215-235. doi:10.1111/aphw.12127.

Karekla, M., Forsyth, J. & Kelly, M. (2004). Emotional avoidance and panicogenic responding to a biological challenge procedure. *Behavior Therapy*, 35(4), 725-746. doi:10.1016/s0005-7894(04)80017-0.

Kirby, J. N. (2017). Compassion interventions: The programmes, the evidence, and implications for research and practice. *Psychology and Psychotherapy: Theory, research and practice*, 90(3), 432-455. doi:10.1111/papt.12104.

Litman, G. K., Stapleton, J., Oppenheim, A. N., Peleg, M. & Jackson, P. (1984). The relationship between coping behaviours, their effectiveness and alcoholism relapse and survival. *British Journal of Addiction*. 79(3), 283-91. doi: 10.1111/j.1360-0443.1984.tb00276.x. PMID: 6595022.

Machell, K. A., Goodman, F. R., & Kashdan, T. B. (2015). Experiential avoidance and wellbeing: A daily diary analysis. *Cognition and Emotion*, 29(2), 351-359. doi:10.1080/02699931.2014.911143.

Marshall, E. J. & Brockman, R. N. (2016). The relationships between Psychological flexibility, self-compassion, and emotional well-being. *Journal of Cognitive Psychotherapy*, 30(1), 60-72. doi:10.1891/0889-8391.30.1.60.

Melamed, S., Groswasser, Z. & Stern, M. (1992). Acceptance of disability, work involvement and subjective rehabilitation status of traumatic brain-injured (TBI) patients. *Brain Injury*, 6(3), 233-243. doi:10.3109/02699059209029665.

- Moroz, M., & Dunkley, D. M. (2019). Self-critical perfectionism, experiential avoidance, and depressive and anxious symptoms over two years: A three-wave longitudinal study. *Behaviour Research and Therapy, 112*, 18-27. doi:10.1016/j.brat.2018.11.006.
- Neff, K. D. (2003). The development and validation of a scale to measure self-compassion. *Self and Identity, 2*(3), 223-250. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/15298860309027>.
- Neff, K. D. (2016). The self-compassion scale is a valid and theoretically coherent measure of self-compassion. *Mindfulness, 7*(1), 264-274. doi:10.1007/s12671-015-0479-3.
- Neff, K. D. (2019). Setting the record straight about the Self-Compassion Scale. *Mindfulness, 10*(1), 200-202. doi: 10.1007/s12671-018-1061-6.
- Neff, K. D., & Germer, C. K. (2013). A pilot study and randomized controlled trial of the mindful self-compassion program. *Journal of Clinical Psychology, 69*(1), 28-44. doi:10.1002/jclp.21923.
- Neff, K., & Germer, C. (2017). Self-Compassion and psychological wellbeing. In Seppälä, E. M., Simon-Thomas, E., Brown, S. L., Worline, M. C., Cameron, C. D., & Doty, J. R. (Eds.). (2017). *The Oxford Handbook of Compassion Science* (pp. 371-386). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Neff, K. D., & Germer, C. K. (2018). *The Mindful Self-Compassion workbook: A proven way to accept yourself, find inner strength, and thrive*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Neff, K. D., Long, P., Knox, M. C., Davidson, O., Kuchar, A., Costigan, A., Williamson, Z., Rohleder, N., Tóth-Király, I., & Breines, J. G. (2018). The forest and the trees: Examining the association of self-compassion and its positive and negative components with psychological functioning. *Self and Identity, 17*(6), 627–645. doi: 10.1080/15298868.2018.1436587
- Neff, K.D., & Tirch, D. (2013). Self-compassion and ACT. In T.B. Kashdan & J. Ciarrochi (Eds.), *Mindfulness, acceptance, and positive psychology: The seven foundations of well-being* (pp. 78–106). Oakland, CA: Context Press/New Harbinger Publications.

- Pais-Ribeiro, J., Silva, I., Ferreira, T., Martins, A., Meneses, R., & Baltar, M. (2007). Validation study of a Portuguese version of the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Psychology, Health & Medicine, 12*(2), 225-237. doi:10.1080/13548500500524088.
- Patrón Espinosa, F. (2010). La Evitación Experiencial y su medición por medio del AAQ-II. *Enseñanza e Investigación en Psicología, 15*(1), 5-19.
- Pinto-Gouveia, J., Gregório, S., Dinis, A., & Xavier, A. (2012). Experiential avoidance in clinical and non-clinical samples: AAQ-II Portuguese version. *International Journal of Psychology and Psychological Therapy, 12*(2), 139-156.
- Preacher, K. J., & Kelley, K. (2011). Effect size measures for mediation models: quantitative strategies for communicating indirect effects. *Psychological Methods, 16*(2), 93. doi:10.1037/a0022658.
- Riegel, B. J. (1993). Contributors to cardiac invalidism after acute myocardial infarction. *Coronary Artery Diseases, 4*(2), 215-20. doi: 10.1097/00019501-199302000-00013.
- Roemer, L., Salters, K., Raffa, S. & Orsillo, S.(2005). Fear and Avoidance of Internal Experiences in GAD: Preliminary Tests of a Conceptual Model. *Cognitive Therapy and Research 29*, 71-88 doi:10.1007/s10608-005-1650-2.
- Rogge, R. D., Daks, J. S., Dubler, B. A., & Saint, K. J. (2019). It's all about the process: Examining the convergent validity, conceptual coverage, unique predictive validity, and clinical utility of ACT process measures. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science, 14*, 90-102. doi: 10.1016/j.jcbs.2019.10.001
- Ruiz, F. J., Herrera, Á. I. L., Luciano, C., Cangas, A. J., & Beltrán, I. (2013). Measuring experiential avoidance and psychological inflexibility: The Spanish version of the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II. *Psicothema, 25*(1), 123-129. doi: 10.7334/psicothema2011.239
- Ryff, C. (1989). Beyond Ponce de Leon and life satisfaction: New directions in quest of successful aging. *International Journal of Behavioral Development, 12*, 35-55. doi:10.1177/016502548901200102

- Shapiro, S. L., Carlson, L. E., Astin, J. A., & Freedman, B. (2006). Mechanisms of mindfulness. *Journal of Clinical Psychology, 62*, 373–386. doi:10.1002/jclp.20237.
- Siegel, R. D., Germer, C. K., & Oldenzki, A. (2009). Mindfulness: What is it? Where does it come from? In F. Didonna (Ed.), *Clinical Handbook of Mindfulness* (pp. 17–35). New York, NY: Springer. doi:10.1007/978-0-387-09593-6_2
- Terol, M. C., López-Roig, S., Rodríguez-Marín, J., Martí-Aragón, M., Pastor, M. A., & Reig, M. T. (2007). Propiedades psicométricas de la escala hospitalaria de ansiedad y depresión (HAD) en población española. *Ansiedad y Estrés, 13*, 163-176.
- Treanor, M. (2011). The potential impact of mindfulness on exposure and extinction learning in anxiety disorders. *Clinical Psychology Review, 31*, 617-625. doi: 10.1016/j.cpr.2011.02.003.
- Tyndall, I., Waldeck, D., Pancani, L., Whelan, R., Roche, B., & Dawson, D. L. (2019). The Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II) as a measure of experiential avoidance: Concerns over discriminant validity. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science, 12*, 278-284. doi: 10.1016/j.jcbs.2018.09.005
- Wilson, A. C., Mackintosh, K., Power, K., & Chan, S. W. (2019). Effectiveness of self-compassion related therapies: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Mindfulness, 10*(6), 979-995. doi:10.1007/s12671-018-1037-6.
- Wolgast, M. (2014). What does the Acceptance and Action Questionnaire (AAQ-II) really measure? *Behavior Therapy, 45*, 831-839. doi: 10.1016/j.beth.2014.07.002
- Yela, J. R., Gómez-Martínez, M. Á., Crego, A., & Jiménez, L. (2020a). Effects of the Mindful Self-Compassion programme on clinical and health psychology trainees' well-being: A pilot study. *Clinical Psychologist, 24*(1), 41-54. doi:10.1111/cp.12204.
- Yela, J. R., Crego, A., Gómez-Martínez, M. Á., & Jiménez, L. (2020b). Self-compassion, meaning in life, and experiential avoidance explain the relationship between meditation and positive mental health outcomes. *Journal of Clinical Psychology, 76* (9), 1631-1652. doi:10.1002/jclp.22932.

Zigmond, A. S., & Snaith, R. P. (1983). The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 67(6), 361-370. doi:10.1111/j.1600-0447.1983.tb09716.x.

Tables

Table 1. Overview of the MSC protocol's sessions

Session	Contents
Session 1: "What is self-compassion"	This first session informs participants of the basic rules of the group and introduces basic aspects of self-compassion. The first tasks are assigned to practice at home: audios and notebook for students will be provided, with the tasks and activities of all sessions.
Session 2: "Practicing mindfulness"	In this session, participants work on any difficulties they may have experienced in daily practice at home, and formal mindfulness practices (requiring specific time dedicated only to those tasks) are introduced. In addition, new tasks and informal mindfulness practices (which can be carried out simultaneously with daily life activities) are added for the week.
Session 3: "Taking care of yourself"	This session reviews the difficulties derived from mindfulness practice and addresses the importance of carrying out self-care activities in relation to the person's psychological needs. Formal (audio) and informal practice tasks are added in areas where people need to develop flexibility on both emotional and behavioral levels.
Session 4: "Self-compassion"	The usefulness of being benevolent to oneself and wishing that the people around us are free from suffering that could affect them is addressed. Strategies are practiced to develop this attitude towards oneself. Specific formal practices for home training are conducted and informal practice tasks and audios are assigned.
Session 5: "Identifying personal values"	The concept of personal value is introduced through activities, so that the person clarifies and identifies his or her own set of goals. Exercises are practiced and informal practice tasks are assigned to be implemented during the week.
Session 6: "Managing difficult emotions"	Strategies are practiced to identify negative emotions and learn to expose oneself to them by developing acceptance through various techniques. As a homework assignment, the person practices formal practice (audios) and concrete acceptance tasks in everyday life.
Session 7: "Transforming difficult relationships"	Formal practice strategies are taught to identify the emotional dimensions involved in maintaining conflictive interpersonal relationships. Also, compassionate interpersonal management skills are trained. Audios of formal practice and informal compassionate time-out practice are used as homework assignments.
Session 8: "Closing"	Development of the ability to appreciate the positive and pleasant elements of our context and personal qualities. Compassionate mindfulness training. Review of what has been learned during the course and preparation for practice outside the group. Questions are resolved for the maintenance of the practice.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and t-test for related samples.

	Pre (N=50)		Post (N=50)		t (49)	r ²
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Self-compassion (total)	2.82	0.68	3.57	0.71	-7.76***	0.55
Self-kindness	2.71	0.87	3.57	0.77	-7.77***	0.55
Common humanity	3.08	0.90	3.69	0.81	-4.24***	0.27
Mindfulness	2.93	0.83	3.69	0.76	-6.21***	0.44
Self-judgment	3.22	0.80	2.50	0.87	5.79***	0.41
Isolation	3.03	0.92	2.39	0.84	4.85***	0.32
Over-identification	3.49	0.87	2.60	0.75	7.99***	0.57
Anxiety	9.08	4.74	7.00	4.17	3.56***	0.21
Depression	5.22	4.24	3.70	3.74	3.20**	0.17
Wellbeing	4.31	0.91	4.62	0.81	-4.05***	0.25

***p<.001; **p<.01

Table 3. Standardized total effects of changes in self-compassion (total and SCS components) on changes in anxiety, depression and wellbeing

	Anxiety			Depression			Wellbeing		
	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB
Self-compassion									
(total)	-0.63**	-0.80	-0.40	-0.63***	-0.80	-0.39	0.84***	0.71	0.94
Self-kindness	-0.53***	-0.74	-0.26	-0.48**	-0.70	-0.20	0.67***	0.44	0.83
Common humanity	-0.48***	-0.68	-0.21	-0.51***	-0.71	-0.26	0.58***	0.35	0.75
Mindfulness	-0.50***	-0.70	-0.23	-0.51***	-0.71	-0.25	0.76***	0.58	0.88
Self-judgment	0.51**	0.24	0.73	0.54***	0.27	0.76	-0.74***	-0.88	-0.56
Isolation	0.48**	0.22	0.69	0.56***	0.31	0.75	-0.73***	-0.86	-0.56
Over-identification	0.63***	0.47	0.84	0.56***	0.30	0.75	-0.69***	-0.84	-0.49

***p<.001; **p<.01; *p<.05; LB: lower bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected Confidence Interval; HB: higher bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected

Confidence Interval; The effects of age and gender were controlled for. In addition, nationality was controlled for in analyses involving self-kindness.

Table 4. Standardized direct effects of changes in self-compassion (total and SCS components) on changes in experiential avoidance, anxiety, depression, and wellbeing.

	Experiential avoidance			Anxiety			Depression			Wellbeing		
	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB
Self-compassion (total)	-0.73***	-0.87	-0.53	-0.37*	-0.66	-0.04	-0.29	-0.58	0.04	0.67***	0.43	0.87
Self-kindness	-0.60***	-0.79	-0.34	-0.24	-0.53	0.05	-0.13	-0.41	0.16	0.39**	0.13	0.62
Common humanity	-0.53***	-0.72	-0.27	-0.22	-0.47	0.06	-0.23	-0.47	0.04	0.31*	0.07	0.53
Mindfulness	-0.55***	-0.74	-0.30	-0.23	-0.49	0.05	-0.21	-0.46	0.06	0.54***	0.33	0.72
Self-judgment	0.64***	0.41	0.82	0.20	-0.11	0.49	0.20	-0.09	0.49	-0.48***	-0.70	-0.23
Isolation	0.62***	0.40	0.79	0.17	-0.12	0.46	0.25	-0.03	0.52	-0.50***	-0.70	-0.27
Over-identification	0.56***	0.32	0.75	0.48***	0.23	0.71	0.27*	0.01	0.52	-0.44***	-0.65	-0.21

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$; LB: lower bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected Confidence Interval; HB: higher bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected

Confidence Interval; The effects of age and gender were controlled for. In addition, nationality was controlled for in analyses involving self-kindness.

Table 5. Standardized direct effects of changes in experiential avoidance on changes in anxiety, depression, and wellbeing.

Independent variable of mediation model:	Standardized direct effects of experiential avoidance on anxiety			Standardized direct effects of experiential avoidance on depression			Standardized direct effects of experiential avoidance on wellbeing		
	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB	Point estimate	LB	HB
Self-compassion (total)	0.36*	0.03	0.64	0.47**	0.15	0.73	-0.23*	-0.45	-0.00
Self-kindness	0.48***	0.18	0.71	0.58***	0.31	0.80	-0.46***	-0.68	-0.23
Common humanity	0.49***	0.21	0.71	0.54***	0.28	0.74	-0.52***	-0.71	-0.28
Mindfulness	0.48***	0.20	0.70	0.55***	0.28	0.75	-0.40***	-0.58	-0.19
Self-judgment	0.49***	0.19	0.73	0.55***	0.26	0.76	-0.40***	-0.62	-0.18
Isolation	0.50***	0.19	0.74	0.51***	0.22	0.73	-0.38***	-0.60	-0.16
Over-identification	0.35**	0.09	0.57	0.52***	0.24	0.72	-0.45***	-0.65	-0.23

***p<.001; **p<.01; *p<.05; LB: lower bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected Confidence Interval; HB: higher bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected

Confidence Interval; The effects of age and gender were controlled for. In addition, nationality was controlled for in analyses involving self-kindness.

Table 6. Proportion of variance (R^2) of the mediator (experiential avoidance change-scores) and outcome variables change-scores explained by models including self-compassion change-scores (total and SCS components) as independent variable.

	Experiential avoidance change-scores R^2	Anxiety change-scores R^2	Depression change-scores R^2	Wellbeing change-scores R^2
Independent variable of mediation model (change- scores):				
Self-compassion (total)	0.50	0.45	0.48	0.70
Self-kindness	0.35	0.42	0.46	0.59
Common humanity	0.29	0.42	0.48	0.56
Mindfulness	0.31	0.42	0.47	0.69
Self-judgment	0.38	0.41	0.46	0.63
Isolation	0.38	0.40	0.48	0.64
Over-identification	0.31	0.53	0.49	0.62

Note: the effects of age and gender were controlled for. In addition, nationality was controlled for in analyses involving self-kindness.

Table 7. Standardized indirect effects of changes in self-compassion (total and SCS components) on changes in anxiety, depression, and wellbeing, through experiential avoidance.

	Anxiety				Depression				Wellbeing			
	Point estimate	LB	HB	IE/TE	Point estimate	LB	HB	IE/TE	Point estimate	LB	HB	IE/TE
Self-compassion (total)	-0.26*	-0.51	-0.04	41.81	-0.34**	-0.59	-0.12	54.24	0.17*	0.01	0.37	19.95
Self-kindness	-0.29***	-0.52	-0.12	54.37	-0.35***	-0.60	-0.18	73.53	0.28***	0.13	0.48	41.89
Common humanity	-0.26***	-0.47	-0.11	53.75	-0.28***	-0.49	-0.13	55.06	0.27***	0.13	0.46	46.82
Mindfulness	-0.27***	-0.48	-0.11	53.20	-0.30***	-0.52	-0.14	58.67	0.22***	0.10	0.38	28.97
Self-judgment	0.32**	0.14	0.56	61.96	0.35***	0.18	0.59	63.97	-0.26***	-0.46	-0.12	34.86
Isolation	0.31**	0.13	0.55	64.18	0.32***	0.15	0.54	56.23	-0.24***	-0.43	-0.10	32.28
Over-identification	0.20**	0.07	0.39	31.53	0.29***	0.14	0.51	51.97	-0.25***	-0.44	-0.12	36.48

***p<.001; **p<.01; *p<.05; LB: lower bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected Confidence Interval; HB: higher bound of 95% Bootstrap Corrected

Confidence Interval; IE/TE: ratio indirect effect/ total effect (in percentage); The effects of age and gender were controlled for. In addition, nationality was controlled for in analyses involving self-kindness.